

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING EXTERNAL SOURCES IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Relevance: The current process requires the use of the most modern sources. However, no matter how up-to-date the textbooks are, they cannot fully satisfy the growing demands and demands for innovations. The use of external sources in language learning increases the effectiveness of the lesson, as well as the students' language learning and application skills, allows them to use a "live" language, increases their interest in the language through the analysis of life problems and situations, and fills in the gaps in the textbook with information that interests and is necessary for students.

Goal: The National Program sets as a priority task not only to provide modern knowledge to young people, but also to instill a correct understanding of nationality.

Material and method: Nationality plays an important role in the life of every nation. Through customs, the imagination, dreams and hopes of the people and the nation, their way of life are expressed. It should be noted that the impact of customs and traditions on socio-spiritual development can be different. This is due to the attitude of the nation to its traditions. In general, no nation lives without customs and traditions. However, the degree of adherence to traditions in life can be different. Customs and traditions also play an important role in the life of the Uzbek people and have a specific impact on socio-cultural development.

Firstly, customs and traditions express the spiritual world of man and serve his spiritual purification and elevation. Secondly, customs and traditions enrich the cultural life of the nation. They ensure its progressive development in connection with its past, present and future. Thirdly, customs and traditions are associated with certain costs. It is necessary to take into account the existence of its material and spiritual aspects. The results in socio-cultural life are manifested in the normative relationship between these aspects.

Result: If attention is paid only to the material aspects of customs and traditions, the tendency increases, and the spiritual significance of any tradition decreases. This situation can have a negative aspect to a certain extent. It is natural that this negatively affects not only socio-economic development, but also the spiritual and moral world of people, the universal human and moral foundations of society, customs and traditions should be inextricably linked with social development. **Conclusion:** Nationality plays an important role in the life of every nation. Through customs, the imagination, dreams and hopes of the people, the nation, their way of life are expressed. The use of external sources helps students not only in language learning, but also in vividly mastering the language through real-life materials and in the future in the process of work.